

Figure 4. Code book with definitions and examples				
Field	Definition	Type of Data	Controlled Entry	Example Data
Author	first author last name	text string	free text	Schneider
Year	publication year	number	free text	2009
Country	country of affiliation of the first author	text string	free text	Germany
DOI	digital object identifier	text string	free text	10.1016/j.toxlet.2009.05.013
Intended Use	how the authors self-subscribe their use or reference of the tool 'ToxRTool'	text string	pick list	study quality
Field of Study	general field of study that best describes the overall subject area	text string	pick list	toxicology
Exposure	the type of exposure the authors describe that their project assesses where this could include the application of substance(s) or environmental factors(s) to affect and outcome and intentional or unintentional exposure	text string	pick list	industrial chemicals
Data Type	the type of data described in the study	text string	pick list	in vitro, in vivo
ToxRTool Use	If the authors indicate they did not modify ToxRTool select 'used as is' and stop data collection in this section. If there are modifications present, select the best response in the next section's questions. The authors followed (F) ToxRTool, modified (M) ToxRTool, added (A) to ToxRTool, Referenced prior publication's modifications (R), or no changes were made (none (N)).	text string	single choice	followed (F)
Notes/Comments	open response for the reviewer to indicate any relevant quotes, observations, summaries, assumptions, unclear data, or noteworthy information. Page numbers and location in the paper should be included for direct quotes.	text string	free text	23 question data quality assessment, combines in vitro/in vivo questions without groupings (i.e., Test Substance Identification), coral case study applies the 23 questions presented in the paper
Changes made to 'Test Substance Identification'	specific modifications, additions, or other changes made to the 'Test Substances Identification' grouping	text string	pick list	modified all the questions
Changes made to 'Test System Characterization'	specific modifications, additions, or other changes made to the 'Test System Characterization' grouping.	text string	pick list	met original questions with modifications
Changes made to 'Study Design Description'	specific modifications, additions, or other changes made to the 'Study Design Description' grouping.	text string	pick list	added a question(s)
Changes made to 'Study Results Documentation'	specific modifications, additions, or other changes made to the 'Study Results Documentation' grouping.	text string	pick list	added a new 'Criteria Group'
Changes made to 'Plausibility of Study Design and Data'	specific modifications, additions, or other changes made to the 'Plausibility of Study Design and Data' grouping.	text string	pick list	developed a new scoring system
Other changes not categorized based on the original ToxRTool 5 groupings	other changes made to ToxRTool that is not covered by the original 5 groupings listed (Test Substance Identification, Test System Characterization, etc.).	text string	pick list	none (not mentioned or addressed)

Figure 4. Code book with definitions and examples. Each row describes a particular field through a definition, the type of data, the controlled entry, and an example of extracted data. For example, for the field 'Country' it is defined as 'the country of affiliation of the first author', the data type is 'text string', the controlled entry is 'free text', and the example data is 'Germany.'